

THE GRAMMATICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADVERBS IN ENGLISH AND ROMANIAN: A CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper presents a contrastive analysis of adverbs in English and Romanian, focusing on their morphological formation, syntactic distribution, and functional characteristics. Although both languages belong to the Indo-European family, they represent distinct branches—Germanic and Romance—resulting in both structural similarities and significant divergences. Drawing on major reference grammar, this study examines the points of convergence and divergence between the adverbial systems of the two languages. The findings indicate parallel morphological mechanisms, particularly in derivation, alongside notable syntactic differences regarding combinatory possibilities and sentence-level modification. Using a comparative methodology, the study establishes the degree of equivalence and distinctness between these categories and their means of expression. This investigation is supported by a corpus of translation examples from both literary and scientific texts, providing a practical basis for the contrastive analysis of these two distantly related languages.

Keywords: adverbial systems, contrastive linguistics, morphology, English grammar, Romanian grammar, derivation.

1. Introduction

Contrastive linguistics aims to identify structural similarities and differences between languages, regardless of their genetic relationship [13]. While traditional comparative philology concentrated on historically related languages, modern contrastive studies emphasize synchronic structural comparison [14]. Such research presupposes that languages share certain universal grammatical categories, even if these categories are realized differently. There has been a constantly growing interest in contrastive linguistics or linguistic confrontation. Sameness and similarity have always been the cornerstone of linguistic confrontation.

The comparative historical study of languages for many years was the unique and the only scientific method in linguistics. However, it gradually gave way to other methods and approaches. Nevertheless, the idea of comparing different languages remained as a guiding principle but the synchronic comparison implies a quest for altogether new sets of features and peculiarities.

For comparative philology these were always thought of as something that was genetically common, something that gradually diverged under the pressure of a variety of structural and extra linguistic factors. Analytical comparison continues seeking a method to compare languages across disparate families by identifying abstract features and distinctive linguistic markers.

Comparison in the widest sense of the word is carried out unless those carrying it out are convinced that there does exist a certain fundamental similarity between the two or more objects under investigation. If there were no underlying assumptions that all languages have something in common, the problem of confrontation simply would not exist.

Confrontational comparison has the advantage over comparative philology of being able to suggest a method which would be applicable to all languages irrespective of their history or possible genetic relationship. In this search we should confront some grammatical categories in English and their equivalents in Romanian. The two languages are distantly related. Comparison of related and unrelated languages is still widely spread but the methodology of their research must be further elaborated.

There is not enough attention paid to the adverbs while teaching English within practical classes at school and university, considering it to be an easy and not so important subject. English grammar is taught paying more attention to such parts of speech as verbs, nouns, pronouns, articles, prepositions, but paying less attention to the adverb as a part of speech which includes words qualifying an action or a quality or expressing various circumstances in which an action takes place. The adverb is usually only mentioned as ending in *-ly* when speaking about adjectives.

During English classes we have realized the difficulties and confusion that students sometimes encounter in making a difference between an adjective and an adverb. They often feel confused using the wrong word when writing sentences and while speaking. Besides there are some adverbs, the use of which is a real problem for the students. The dilemma is what and how to use: “good” or “well”, “bad” or “badly” and when. It is also important to know that some adjectives can also end in *-ly*, like the adverbs do. For example: “The friendly people welcomed to the neighborhood”.

So, the students must be taught the difference between adjectives and adverbs, i.e. figuring out the question of a modifier answers we are able to tell whether the modifier is an adjective or an adverb.

Nevertheless, some words can be either nouns or adverbs of time or place depending on how we use them in a sentence. For example, words like “yesterday”, “today”, “tomorrow” can function as nouns or as adverbs of time. Words that include “home”: “uptown”, “downstairs”, “outdoors” etc. can be both: nouns or adverbs of place.

The practical aspect of this article describes the characteristics of adverbs in Romanian, which also have their specific peculiarities. There are a great number of adverbs being different according to their origin and the way they are formed. As in English, the adverbs in Romanian have derived from adjectives, but in some cases nouns, pronouns even numerals can be used as adverbs. Thus, the adverb appears in both languages to be a part of speech which is tightly connected to almost all parts of speech, especially with adjectives, so that we have revealed numerous interesting aspects while studying the historical evolution of the English adverb as a part of speech. The study confirms the intrinsic link between the adjective and the adverb, focusing on the morphological derivation of the latter.

2. Theoretical Framework: The Adverb as a Grammatical Category

In English grammar, adverbs are traditionally defined as modifiers of verbs, adjectives, other adverbs, and occasionally entire clauses [9,12]. However, modern grammatical descriptions emphasize that “adverb” is not a uniform category but rather a residual class defined partly by distributional criteria [12]. We may distinguish between:

- Adjuncts
- Disjuncts
- Conjuncts

This functional classification highlights the role of adverbs at both clause and sentence level [17].

In Romanian grammar, the adverb is defined as an invariable part of speech expressing circumstances or characteristics of actions and states [2,7]. Like English adverbs, Romanian adverbs are morphologically invariable, though some admit degrees of comparison.

3. Morphological Formation of Adverbs

English adverbs may be classified morphologically as:

1. **Simple adverbs:** *now, here, then, well*
2. **Derived adverbs:** typically, with the suffix *-ly*
3. **Compound adverbs:** *sometimes, somewhere*
4. **Adverbial phrases:** *at least, at last* [8,17]

The suffix *-ly* is the primary productive marker of adverb formation in English. It attaches mainly to qualitative adjectives [16]. For example: *quick* → *quickly*; *serious* → *seriously*

According to [4], the suffix *-ly* historically derives from Old English *-lic*, which also produced adjectival forms. This explains why some words ending in *-ly* are adjectives rather than adverbs (e.g., *friendly, daily*). Corpus-based research further demonstrates that *-ly* adverbs vary in frequency and register distribution [6].

Certain words can be either adjectives or adverbs, depending on the way we use them in a sentence. To decide whether a word is an adjective or an adverb one should consider the word it defines or modifies. If the modified word is a noun or a pronoun, the modifier is an adjective. If the modified word is a verb or an adjective, then the modifier is an adverb.

- e.g. Hilda likes hard candy.
(The adjective “hard” describes the noun “candy”)
- e.g. Hilda bit hard on a candy.
(The adverb “hard” tells how Hilda bit into the candy)

Other words that can be either adverbs or adjectives include: “well”, “early”, “long”, “late”, and “low”.

Many words end in *-ly* but so do some adjectives:
e.g. The actor performed brilliantly in the play.
(Adverb)

e.g. Friendly people welcomed us to the neighborhood [15]. (Adjective)

Thus, in the second example one can notice that even though “friendly” end in *-ly* it is an adjective.

Alternatively, if one can figure out which question a modifier answers, it can tell whether the modifier is an adverb or an adjective.

Adjective:	Adverb:
1. Which	1. How or in what manner?
2. What kind (of)	2. When?
3. How many	3. Where?
	4. How often?
	5. To what extent or degree?

e.g. Is that a daily newspaper?

Analysis: “Daily” modifies “newspaper” which is a noun. “Daily” tells what kind. Therefore “daily” is an adjective.

e.g. We bake our bread daily.

Analysis: “Daily” modifies “bake” which is a verb. “Daily” tells how often. Therefore “daily” is an adverb.

Many doubts are expressed sometimes to “good” and “well”, “bad” and “badly”.

“Good” and “bad” are always adjective. “Badly” is always and adverb. “Well,” can be an adverb of manner, as it can be noticed in the following example:

e.g. He drove well. (meaning skillfully)

But “well” can be also an adjective:

e.g. He is well [15.] (meaning “in good health”)

The following chart shows the different uses of each word:

	Good	Well
Adjective (after linking verb)	e.g. I feel good. (in good health, healthy) e.g. I look good at that. (well dressed)	e.g. I feel well. (in good health, satisfactory)
Adverb (after action verb)	-	e.g. I play well. (how, the way I play)

	Bad	Badly
Adjective (after linking word)	e.g. I feel bad. (in poor condition; sad) e.g. I look bad. (in poor health)	-
Adverb (after action verb)	-	e.g. It hurts badly. (how, the way it hurts)

To summarize, the correct application of these terms is predicated on the syntactic function of the verb within the clause. The selection of a modifier—whether an adjective or an adverb—is not arbitrary but rather strictly dictated by whether the verb establishes a state of being or describes a dynamic action.

4. Noun or Adverb

Noun	Adverb
e.g. Yesterday was eventful. e.g. Today is a holiday. e.g. The great outdoors is beautiful.	e.g. We were busy yesterday. (adverb of time) e.g. We will celebrate today. (adverb of time) e.g. Children must play outdoors. (adverb of place) [15]

Some words can be either nouns or adverbs of time or place, depending on the way they are being used in a sentence. Words like “yesterday”, “today”, “tomorrow” can function as nouns or adverbs of time. Words that can be both nouns and adverbs of place include: “home”, “uptown”, “downstairs”, and “outdoors”.

The words “not” and “never” are negative adverbs. They tell what extent (not at all) and when (never).

- e.g. The last goal did not count.
 (“not” modifies “did count”)
e.g. Lance will never go camping.
 (“never” modifies “will go”)

Other negative words are *nowhere*, *hardly*, *only*.

One should also consider the following two main rules when dealing with negative words to avoid errors with adverbs:

Rule 1. Ordinarily do not use two negative words (a double negative) in the same clause. There should be one negative used only to express the idea of a negative.

Not	I never ate none of that fudge.
But	I <u>never</u> ate <u>any</u> of that fudge.
Not	They do not have brownies .
But	They do <u>not</u> have <u>any</u> brownies.

Rule 2. Place adverbs of degree as close as possibly to the words they modify. Misplaced adverbs make a sentence confusing:

Not	He has almost completed all his chores. (Has he not finished any of them?)
But	He has completed <u>almost</u> all his chores. (he has finished most of them)

Thus, the rules governing negation and adverb placement are essential for maintaining both semantic consistency and structural integrity in English composition. Ultimately, these conventions serve to eliminate ambiguity, ensuring that the reader interprets the text exactly as the writer intended.

5. Adverbs in Romanian

Some languages, either because of genetic identity or because of certain socio-linguistic, historic and other circumstances, are readily confronted, while others are

not. It is easier to translate a text from English into French and Romanian, than from English into Chinese or Arabic. The obvious reason here being the much greater affinity between English, French and Romanian, than between English and Chinese or other unrelated languages.

Thus, the classification of adverbs from the two languages under study (English and Romanian) was confronted altogether with the degrees of comparison

of adverbs, the negation as a phenomenon and finally the syntactical functions in both languages.

We must begin with the definition of the adverb: "The adverb is an inflexible part of speech which expresses a characteristic of the action or state (merge repede; doarme afară; s-a oprit aici) [2].

The adverb is first a verbal determiner. Except the verb, the adverb in Romanian may determine an adjective (puțin urâtă; problemă foarte grea), a noun (scrisoare de acasă), a pronoun (cei de acolo), a numeral (încă doi), or an interjection (ei bine; hai înăuntrul).

It is evident that the adverbs in Romanian can modify even interjections and numerals, while according to the definition given in [9,13], adverbs can modify only verbs, adjectives or another adverb.

It is also important to note that in Romanian there are adverbs that are themselves sentences. For example: "da" and "nu" or predicative adverbs like "bineînțeles", "desigur", "firește". Some adverbs "chiar", "tocmai", "nu numai", "poate" give an additional meaning to a whole sentence or only to a part of this sentence:

e.g. Tocmai azi dimineață am sosit de la Florența.

e.g. Poate demult s-a stins în drum.

e.g. În depărtări albastre [2].

In comparison with other parts of speech, the adverb in Romanian and English is inflexible, which means it does not have declination, it is not conjugated and does not change its genre. Some adverbs have degrees of comparison, like adjectives, also expressed analytically with the help of auxiliary words.

6. Morphological classification of adverbial systems

Taking into consideration the origin and formation of the English and Romanian adverb we have noticed that in many aspects the adverbs of the two languages, i.e. their principles of the morphological classification coincide.

Some grammarians [8] suggest that according to the form of the adverbs in English may be classified as follows:

a) Simple adverbs which have no ending show that they are adverbs. For example: here, how, then, now, quiet, still.

b) Derived adverbs formed from other parts of speech by composition. For example: sometimes, somewhere, midway [8,17].

Most adverbs are derived from qualitative adjectives by means of adding the suffix "-ly". For example: slowly, quickly, seriously, actively etc.

Much rare adverbs are formed by the addition of the suffix "-ly" to the stem of:

1. participles (inquiringly, meaningly, decidedly)

2. nouns (partly, bodily)

c) Phrase adverbs formed from nouns with prepositions (phraseological units). For example: at last, at least, one by one, to and from etc.)

d) Combinations of an adverb with preposition such as till, now, since, then, from, where, from within etc.)

Having analyzed the classification of adverbs according to their origin and formation presented in [5], and having studied the classification of the Romanian

adverbs, while taking into consideration the same principles used for the classification of the adverbs in English, we have come to the following morphological classification:

a) Simple adverbs, i.e. those which have no specific ending (acum, agale, atunci, deja, aici, poate etc.)

b) Derived adverbs formed from other parts of speech (bărbătește, haiducește, omenește etc.) So, as most adverbs in Romanian derived from qualitative adjectives by adding the suffixes: "-ește" and "-icește". For example: nebunește, moldovenește, părintește etc.

c) Compound adverbs, those combined with other words:

1. nouns (măine seara, ieri noapte)

2. prepositions (de-abia, de dinainte, până acum)

3. adverbs (oarecum, orișicum, oriunde) [5,7].

In conclusion, the morphological classification of Romanian adverbs into simple, derived, and compound forms demonstrates a clear and systematic structural organization. The productivity of derivational suffixes such as *-ește* and *-icește* highlights the close relationship between adjectives and adverbs, while the existence of compound formations illustrates the flexibility and richness of adverbial expression. This framework not only clarifies the internal mechanisms of Romanian adverb formation but also supports meaningful comparison with corresponding structures in English.

7. Conclusions

To sum up, the adverb constitutes a complex and multifunctional grammatical category in both English and Romanian. Although both languages employ productive derivational mechanisms and analytic comparison, Romanian exhibits greater syntactic flexibility and different negation patterns. Since the adverb does denote qualifications of the second order, not of the first one, like adjectives, it includes a great number of semantically weakened words which are in fact intermediate lexemes by their status and often display features of pronominal nature both in English and Romanian.

Furthermore, the morphological classification of adverbs in English and Romanian is similar in the following points:

1. There are simple adverbs in English and Romanian, and they even coincide (in English: here, in Romanian: aici)

2. There are derived adverbs formed from different parts of speech in both languages.

3. In both languages a suffix (suffixes) is used to denote some adverbs. (In English "-ly", in Romanian "-ește, -icește")

Finally, in both languages, adverbs may appear in combination with adjectives, nouns, prepositions, and participles; however, Romanian adverbs also display the capacity to combine with verbs, a feature that does not characterize the English adverb to the same extent. Therefore, while certain structural differences can be identified, the overall comparison highlights substantial parallels between the two languages.

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